

Assessment of Rural Youths' Involvement in Agricultural Activities in Kwara State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The future of agriculture in the country may be bleak, as the bulk of the production efforts rests in the hands of aged subsistence farmers. This study analyzed the rural youths' involvement in agricultural activities in Kwara State, Nigeria, and specifically described the socio-economic characteristics of rural youths, determined their attitudes towards agricultural activities, identified the factors encouraging their involvement in agricultural activities, identified their extent of involvement in agricultural activities, and examined the constraints to their involvement. A four-stage sampling procedure was used to select 150 youths, and data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and chi-square analysis. The results showed that more than half (53.3%) were male, and their mean age was approximately 25 years. The youths exhibited positive attitudes as 'Agriculture increased food production' ($\bar{x}=4.16$) ranked 1st. The major factor encouraging their involvement was 'Access to agricultural training programs' ($\bar{x}=4.01$). The youths were more involved in on-farm (GM= 1.17) and non-farm (GM= 0.96) activities. The major constraint hindering their involvement was inadequate initial capital ($\bar{x}=2.58$). Gender ($X^2=12.46$, $p=0.000$), marital status ($X^2=15.83$, $p=0.000$), educational level ($X^2=28.41$, $p=0.000$), and source of information ($X^2=18.54$, $p=0.000$) of the youths were statistically significant with their involvement. The study concluded that while the rural youths were actively involved in agricultural activities, their full potential could only be realized if they were provided with adequate support. It was recommended that the government and non-governmental organizations should make credit facilities accessible and subsidize farm inputs to encourage maximum involvement in agricultural activities.

Keywords: Rural youths, Involvement, Agricultural activities, Assessment

INTRODUCTION

For all developing countries globally, agriculture is an essential sub-sector for economic viability and social stability (Pawlak & Kolodziejczak, 2020). In many developing countries, most agricultural production is still in the hands of older farmers, which currently makes up the majority of the agricultural population in Nigeria. The elders' agricultural productivity level cannot meet the speedily growing population's food and fibre needs (Akano et al., 2023). The youth constitute the major base for any country that is committed to sustainable agricultural and rural development policies. Youths in the agriculture programme have been described as a very important structure for land and agrarian reform, which will go a long way towards promoting the interests of youths in the agricultural sector of the economy (Msangi et al., 2024).

The agricultural status and agricultural workforce of Nigeria play a crucial role in its socioeconomic development. Now, Agriculture is entrepreneurial and technology-driven. In this way, it is a viable project to expand modern and contemporary technology dissemination for agricultural, animal husbandry, aquaculture, and forestry driven by adolescent-young engagement. Therefore, thousands of idle rural youths will be included in the development process (Yogi et al., 2025). Furthermore, rural youth dream of achieving their full potential to become an emerging force against poverty, deprivation, hunger, and unemployment

(Ng'atigwa et al., 2020). The agricultural future of many developing countries will be bleak if the majority of production efforts fall into the hands of older subsistence farmers (who currently comprise a large percentage of the agricultural sector) as these older farmers are not productive enough to meet food and fiber needs of an ever-growing population and are also not able to sustain themselves as farmers for much longer because of their old age (Henning et al., 2022). Thus, it is important to foster youth involvement in agriculture.

According to Ogunmodede et al. (2020), youths are a dynamic and productive component of human resources who have the capacity to meet development needs, including agriculture; however, despite the existing research surrounding youth participation in agriculture, there remains a call for research to address gaps in knowledge about the significance and challenges of rural youth participation in agriculture. This study specifically;

- i. described the socio-economic characteristics of rural youths,
- ii. determined the attitudes of youths towards agricultural activities;
- iii. identified the factors encouraging rural youths' involvement in agricultural activities;
- iv. identified the extent of involvement of rural youths in agriculture; and
- v. identified the constraints to rural youth involvement in agriculture

The study also tested one hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant relationship between some selected socio-economic characteristics and rural youths' involvement in agricultural activities.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Kwara State, Nigeria. Kwara State is a state in the North-Central Geopolitical Region of Nigeria, within Latitude 8.5°North to 9.5°North and Longitude 3.5°East to 5.5°East. Kwara State borders Niger to the north, Kogi to the east, Ekiti and Osun to the south, and Oyo to the west. It covers a total land area of about 36,825 square kilometers. It was founded on May 27, 1967, and its capital is Ilorin. There are 16 Local Government Areas (LGAs) in the state, and KWADP (Kwara State Agricultural Development Project) subdivides the 16 LGAs into 4 zones. The state is known for its agricultural production, with yams, maize, cassava, tomatoes, and rice being the main crops grown, and also rich in natural resources (Ajadi et al., 2020).

A four-stage sampling procedure was used to select respondents for this study. The first stage involved the purposive selection of three (3) out of the four (4) agricultural zones (ADP), which were zones B, C, and D, because of the prevalence of agricultural activities in the zones. The second stage also involved the purposive selection of two local government areas from each of the zones, which were Zone B (Edu and Patigi), Zone C (Asa and Moro), and Zone D (Ifelodun and Isin) due to observe high Involvement of youths in agricultural activities. The third stage involved the random selection of one community per local government area, which was Edu (Shonga), Patigi (Fey), Asa (Ago-oja), Moro (Malete), Ifelodun (Amoyo), and Isin (Ijara-isin). The fourth stage involved random sampling of 25 youths per community, making a total of 150 respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics of the youth farmers

According to the discoveries in Table 1, male rural youths represented 53.3% of the population, and

54.0% were single. Thus, it can be said that there is a tendency for married youths to possess a greater inclination to venture into agricultural activities compared to singles. This was also confirmed by the findings of Okunlola et. al (2022), who showed that they had more socio-economic expectations to meet than their single counterparts. Furthermore, the modal age of youths was between 21 and 30 years, while the mean age was determined to be 25years. This implies that respondents of young age are very active and contribute to the agricultural sector based on energetic and innovative inputs, as corroborated by the findings of Afolabi et al. (2024).

According to Table 1, it was determined that a majority (86.0%) of the respondents reached post-primary level of education, and a small number (4.0%) of the youths had no education. Therefore, it implies that the youths who received basic education are much more positioned to engage in agricultural activities, which is supported by Ng'atigwa et al. (2020), who determined that educated youths are more likely to accept and engage with new agricultural initiatives and do so faster than those who are uneducated. Furthermore, according to the Table, it was determined that 56.0% of the rural youths had household sizes of 4 persons to 6persons and the average household size is anticipated to be about 5persons. This means that the respondents had a slightly larger family size, which would help out with farming activities, since this was supported by the findings of Mukaila et al. (2020).

In addition, more than half (51.3%) of the rural youths had farming as their primary occupation, while only 8.67% of the youths were civil servants. Also, 38.0% of the rural youths picked the internet as their primary source of farming information. This implies that rural youths' involvement in agricultural activities may be influenced by their access to and use of internet-based information. This corroborates that internet use has a significant impact on the change of rural labor from agricultural to non-agricultural work (Yuan & Fu 2025).

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents

Characteristics	Frequency (n=150)	Percentage	Mean
Gender			
Male	80	53.3	
Female	70	46.7	
Marital Status			
Single	81	54.0	
Married	63	42.0	
Divorced	1	0.7	
Widow	5	3.3	
Age (years)			
≤20	39	26.0	
21 – 30	84	56.0	25.21 (5.57)
31 – 40	27	18.0	
Educational Level			
No formal Education	6	4.0	
Adult Education	10	6.7	
Primary Education	5	3.3	
Secondary Education	65	43.3	
Tertiary Education	64	42.7	
Household Size			
≤3	41	27.3	
4 – 6	84	56.1	
7 – 9	23	15.3	4.77 (1.88)
>9	2	1.3	
Primary Occupation			
Civil Service	26	8.7	
Trading	80	26.7	
Farming	154	51.3	
Others	40	13.3	
Secondary Occupation			
Tailoring	40	26.7	
Bricklaying	27	18.0	
Hairdressing	34	22.7	
Others	49	32.6	
Farming Status			
Full time	41	27.3	
Part time	36	24.0	
Not applicable	73	48.7	
Source of farming Information			
Friends	74	24.7	
Neighbours	52	17.3	
Fellow farmers	28	9.3	
Internet	114	38.0	
Others	32	10.7	

Source: Field survey, 2025

Attitudes of rural youths towards agricultural activities

Table 2 revealed that the highest-ranked attitude statement the youths agreed with was that agriculture increased food production (mean= 4.16). This was followed by “Job creation” (mean= 4.08), “Agriculture is a profitable business enterprise”

(mean= 4.00), “Agriculture improves standard of living” (mean= 3.96), “Farming is stressful and energy-consuming” (mean= 3.85), as the second, third, fourth, and fifth ranked perceived attitude of youths towards agricultural activities. The least agreed-upon attitude statement among the youths in the study area was that agriculture is a bad business

(mean= 2.77). This implies that the respondents in the study area view agriculture as a profitable and beneficial sector, especially in terms of food security, job creation, profitability, and enhancing living standards. Such an attitude implies that there is a possibility of youths watching and possibly practicing agriculture as a driver of the economy and development (Geza et al., 2021).

The aggregate mean of 3.58, which is greater than the neutral average (3.0) of a 1-5 scale, the acceptable statistic of generalized positivity towards agriculture

suggests that respondents understand the economic, social, and developmental benefits of the agricultural industry (Mweta et al., 2025). Since the negative findings relative to income and social status were low, they did not compromise an overwhelmingly positive perception. Therefore, it is reasonable to state that respondents generally possess a positive and progressive perception of agriculture as a practice, an enterprise for self and for development that is productive, skill-enhancing, and income-earning, as well as a sustainable endeavor.

Table 2: Attitudes of rural youths towards agricultural activities

ATTITUDES	SA	A	N	D	SD	MS	GM	Rank
Agriculture increased food production	42.7	39.3	11.3	4.7	2.0	4.16		1 st
Job creation	32.7	48.7	14.7	2.0	2.0	4.08		2 nd
Agriculture is a profitable business enterprise	38.7	36.0	15.3	6.7	3.3	4.00		3 rd
Agriculture improves the standard of living	34.0	39.3	18.0	6.0	2.7	3.96		4 th
Farming is stressful and energy-consuming	34.0	37.3	13.3	10.7	4.7	3.85	3.58	5 th
Skill development	29.3	32.7	27.3	6.7	4.0	3.77		6 th
Farming generates low income	35.3	16.7	8.0	25.3	14.7	3.33		7 th
Farming promotes poverty	16.7	22.7	20.0	30.7	10.0	3.05		8 th
Agriculture should be practiced by the less privileged	19.3	18.0	14.0	24.0	24.7	2.83		9 th
Farming is a bad business	15.3	18.0	12.7	36.7	17.3	2.77		10 th

Source: Field Survey, 2025; Keys: SA- Strongly agree, A- Agree, N- Neutral, D- Disagree, SD- Strongly disagree, MS- Mean score, GM- Grand mean

Factors encouraging Youths' involvement in agricultural activities

From Table 3, the highest-ranked factor encouraging the participation of rural youths in agricultural activities was "Access to mentorship and guidance from experienced farmers or agricultural professionals" (mean= 4.05). This was followed by "Access to agricultural training programs" (mean= 4.03), as the second-ranked factor that encourages

rural youths' participation in agricultural activities. The third-ranked factor that encouraged rural youths' participation in agricultural activities was "Entrepreneurial opportunities within the agricultural sector" (mean= 3.95), while the least ranked factor that influenced the participation of rural youths in agricultural activities was "Family traditions and cultural values" (mean= 3.44). Thus, the majority of the youths did not perceive family traditions and

cultural values to be a significant factor that encourages participation of rural youths in

agricultural activities (Henning et al., 2022).

Table 3: Factors encouraging rural youths' involvement in agricultural activities

FACTORS	SA	A	N	D	SD	MS	Rank
Access to mentorship and guidance from experienced farmers or agricultural professionals	47.3	22.0	22.0	5.3	3.3	4.05	1 st
Access to agricultural training programs	40.0	36.0	14.7	6.0	3.3	4.03	2 nd
Entrepreneurial opportunities within the agricultural sector	37.3	33.3	19.3	6.7	3.3	3.95	3 rd
Financial incentives such as subsidies and grants	30.7	38.7	20.0	7.3	3.3	3.86	4 th
Government policies and initiatives	32.7	36.0	18.7	7.3	5.3	3.83	5 th
Market opportunities	28.0	40.0	23.3	4.0	4.7	3.82	6 th
Environmental awareness and sustainability concerns	34.7	31.3	20.0	8.0	6.0	3.81	7 th
Infrastructural development	26.7	41.3	21.3	8.0	2.7	3.81	7 th
Educational programs	31.3	34.0	22.0	8.7	4.0	3.80	9 th
Family traditions and cultural values	13.3	42.0	26.0	12.7	6.0	3.44	10 th

Source: Field Survey, 2025; **Keys:** SA- Strongly agree, A- Agree, N- Neutral, D- Disagree, SD- Strongly disagree

Extent of youths' involvement in agricultural activities

Results of on-farm agricultural activities the youths were involved in, in Table 4 showed that “Crop cultivation” (mean= 1.59) was ranked first, “Livestock management” (mean= 1.26) was ranked second, while “Nomadic herding” (mean= 0.89) was ranked least. This implies that the respondents were mainly involved in crop cultivation and livestock management, which could be due to a relatively high income earned from these on-farm activities, which aligns with the findings of Chipfupa et al. (2025) that farmers engaged in mixed farming (both crop and livestock) earned significantly higher incomes compared to those involved in crop only or livestock only farming.

For the off-farm agricultural activities, Table 4 showed that “Agribusiness” (mean= 1.03) was the highest-ranked off-farm agricultural activity in which the respondents were involved. “Handcrafting” (mean= 1.01) was ranked second, while “Agro-forestry” (mean= 0.85) was ranked as the least off-

farm agricultural activity the youths were involved in. The fact that agribusiness was ranked the highest had a positive impact to the youths, as there is high potential in agribusiness activities in providing job opportunities and stable income. This is similar to the findings of Mulema et al. (2021), who submitted that the majority of youths in Zambia had a positive disposition that the agricultural sector had high potential in contributing to their livelihoods.

For the non-farm agricultural activities, Table 4 further revealed that “Education” (mean= 1.93) was the highest-ranked non-farm activity that the rural youths were involved in. This was followed by “Healthcare” (mean= 1.05), while “Transportation” (mean= 0.89) was ranked as the least non-farm activity the respondents were involved in. This suggests that the rural youth are more engaged in education than other types of agricultural non-farm occupations, suggesting a high emphasis on building off capacities and skill sets. This can be an investment in human capital development, which will eventually lead to higher employability and

productivity in agricultural and non-agricultural sectors (Adeyanju et al., 2023).

It can also be deduced from Table 4 that the top-most activity the rural youths were involved in was “Education”, followed by “Agribusiness” and then “Crop cultivation”. The least ranked activity the youths were generally involved in was Agro-forestry. This finding implies that rural youths in the study area place a strong emphasis on education, suggesting a prioritization of skill acquisition and capacity building, possibly as a pathway to improved livelihood opportunities. The prominence of agribusiness and crop cultivation as subsequent activities indicates that while youths are still actively engaged in agricultural production, there is a growing interest in value-added and entrepreneurial aspects of the sector, as seen in a similar study by Akrong and Kotu (2021).

Overall, the grand mean of 1.77 indicates low levels of on-farm agricultural engagement. Although it appears that cultivating crops is the most frequently engaged activity, the low mean scores across the board are indicative of the respondents' relatively low engagement in agricultural activities because they are financially, technically, or physically incapable of more, as found in a similar study by Fasakin et al.

(2022). Also, the grand mean of 1.12 suggests a low diversification of livelihood strategies in which respondents engaged. While participation in agribusiness is relatively higher, that of any other off-farm activity is relatively low. This means that the respondents' income-generating activities are still overly farm-based, and they have not yet delved into enough other potentially income-generating strategies that could foster household stability and sustainable livelihoods for the community (Ikuemonisan, 2024).

Yet, the lower mean means, despite almost every other situation, indicates that respondents did not often respond that they had done the off-farm endeavors surveyed, which means that their predominantly agricultural income-generating efforts are overwhelmingly used as a way to survive (Abera et al., 2021). But this is not the case for the grand mean of education employment, as the second grand mean (most valued response) shows that for those who do divert efforts from the farm, it's for more stable employment opportunities that align with social value. Thus, the overall grand mean of 0.96 suggests that there are not many opportunities to supplement income off the farm because the grand mean suggests that a few people are involved in off-farm activities to supplement income, but not enough to matter.

Table 4: Involvement of rural youths in agricultural activities

INVOLVEMENT	HI	MI	MII	NI	MS	Rank	GM
ON-FARM ACTIVITIES							
Crop cultivation	42.7	12.7	5.3	39.3	1.59	1 st	1.17
Livestock management	14.7	36.0	10.0	39.3	1.26	2 nd	
Mixed farming	27.3	15.3	8.0	49.8	1.21	3 rd	
Soil management	15.3	16.0	12.0	56.7	0.9	4 th	
Nomadic herding	18.0	13.3	8.7	60.0	0.89	5 th	
OFF-FARM ACTIVITIES							
Agribusiness	40.7	20.7	10.7	28.0	1.74	1 st	1.12
Handcrafting	16.7	20.0	12.7	50.7	1.03	2 nd	
Agricultural training	17.3	19.3	10.7	52.7	1.01	3 rd	
Agri-tourism	20.0	15.3	7.3	57.3	0.98	4 th	
Agro-forestry	10.0	21.3	12.0	56.7	0.85	5 th	
NON-FARM ACTIVITIES							
Education	38.7	30.7	15.3	15.3	1.93	1 st	0.96
Healthcare	24.7	10.7	9.3	55.3	1.05	2 nd	
Construction	16.7	19.3	10.7	53.3	0.99	3 rd	
Manufacturing	16.0	18.7	9.3	56.0	0.95	4 th	
Transportation	9.3	25.33	10.0	55.3	0.89	5 th	

Source: Field Survey, 2025; Keys: HI= Highly Involved, MI= Moderately Involved, MII= Minimally Involved, NI= Not Involved, WS= Weighted Score, MS= Mean Score, GM- Grand Mean

Constraints to rural youths' involvement in agricultural activities

Table 5 indicates that the most severe constraints to rural youths' involvement in agriculture were lack of initial capital (mean= 2.58), lack of access to tractors (mean= 2.07), lack of transportation means (mean= 2.06), while the least constraint was parental influence (mean= 1.67). This reveals that infrastructural and financial aspects are the major hindrances to rural youth adopting agriculture. Lack of start-up capital, combined with poor access to mechanization and transport, means that without special interventions such as farm equipment assistance, youth credit schemes, and rural roads construction, youths' involvement in the sector can be

low. The low rate of parental influence means family attitudes are not deterrents, suggesting efforts to overcome structural constraints can play an important role with young people in agriculture (Elsayed, 2024).

In summary, the use of the 2.00 grand mean benchmark clarifies the relative importance of each constraint; any mean above the benchmark shows an above-average severity of the constraints, and any mean below suggests a below-average severity of the constraints.

Table 5: Constraints to rural youths' involvement in agricultural activities

CONSTRAINTS	VS	S	NS	NC	MS	GM	Rank
Inadequate initial capital	68.0	26.0	2.0	4.0	2.58		1 st
Poor access to tractors and farm inputs	30.0	52.0	13.33	4.67	2.07		2 nd
Inadequate transportation means	36.0	41.33	16.0	6.67	2.06		3 rd
Poor storage facilities	42.67	32.0	13.33	12.0	2.05		4 th
Climate change	34.67	45.33	10.67	9.33	2.05		4 th
Inadequate access to extension service	36.67	34.0	16.0	13.33	1.94	2.00	6 th
Poor ready market for produce	37.33	33.33	14.67	14.67	1.93		7 th
Poor basic farming knowledge	34.0	35.33	17.33	13.33	1.9		8 th
Farmers are not respected	29.33	38.67	8.0	24.0	1.73		9 th
Parental influence	28.0	32.67	18.0	21.33	1.67		10 th

Source: Field Survey, 2024; Keys: VS- Very severe, S- Severe, NS-Not severe, NC- Not a constraint, MS- Mean score, GM- Grand mean

Hypothesis testing

The result showed that socio-economic characteristics of the respondents had a significant relationship with the level of involvement of the youths in on-farm, off-farm, and non-farm agricultural activities, at $p < 0.05$ significance level. The result from Table 6 revealed that the gender of the respondents was significantly related ($X^2 = 12.46$,

$p = 0.000$) with the youths' involvement in agricultural activities. This suggests that whether a youth is male or female influences their involvement in agricultural activities, which aligns with the findings of Ajaero et al. (2018) and Okeke and Okoye (2021), who identified gender as a critical determinant of agricultural involvement among young people in Nigeria.

Table 6: Chi-square result of the relationship between socio-economic characteristics and youths' involvement in agricultural activities

Socio-economic characteristics	Chi-square	Significance
Gender	12.46**	0.000
Marital status	15.83**	0.000
Educational status	28.41**	0.000
Source of information	18.54**	0.000

** significant at 5% statistical level

Also, Table 6 showed a significant relationship between the youth's marital status ($X^2=15.83$, $p=0.000$) and their involvement in agricultural activities. This reveals that married youths may be more involved in agricultural activities due to family responsibilities. Adepoju and Obayelu (2013) and Akinbile et al. (2021) also found in their studies that marital status influenced the level of participation in farming, as married individuals are often more committed to agricultural ventures than their unmarried counterparts.

Result of educational level ($X^2=28.41$, $p=0.000$) in Table 6 revealed a significant relationship with involvement in agricultural activities. This implies that youths are more likely to participate actively in agriculture, possibly because education improves awareness and adoption of modern farming techniques. Education has been widely recognized as a key factor influencing agricultural productivity and youth engagement, as it enhances decision-making, openness to innovation, and the use of improved agricultural practices (Odetola & Etumnu, 2019)

Also, the source of information ($X^2=18.54$, $p=0.000$) of the youths was statistically significant with their involvement. This shows that youths who access agricultural information through the internet, extension agents, or professional farmers are more likely to be actively engaged than those relying on

friends or family. Access to timely and credible agricultural information has been shown to influence knowledge, skills, and adoption of improved practices, thereby enhancing youth participation in farming (Agwu et al., 2008; Daudu et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study has shown that the highest-ranked attitude statement the youths agreed to was that agriculture increased food production. Also, the rural youths were more involved in crop cultivation, agribusiness, and education. The highest-ranked factor perceived to influence the participation of rural youths in agricultural activities was access to mentorship and guidance from experienced farmers or agricultural professionals, and the most severe constraint to rural youths' involvement in agriculture was inadequate initial capital. The socio-economic characteristics of the rural youths had significant relationships with the rural youths' involvement in agricultural activities. Therefore, the study recommends that the Government and NGOs should make agricultural credit facilities accessible to rural youths to encourage their involvement in agriculture. Also, relevant bodies should organize workshops and training to sensitize rural youths on best practices that can improve agricultural production and make agriculture lucrative to rural youths.

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